

A tale of two islands: Ant diversity on Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands

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Abstract

Ellison (2012) found unexpectedly high ant diversity on Nantucket Island - about 50% of the species and 70% of the genera found in all of New England. The closely affiliated islands of Tuckernuck and Muskeget, while much smaller in size, might also be expected to have relatively high species diversity for their areas. Using the equilibrium island biogeography area equation, $S=cA^z$, we predicted 16 to 33 species for Tuckernuck Island and 11 to 29 species for Muskeget Island.

We tested these predictions by sampling ants with pitfall traps, baits, hand collections and litter samples along ten transects on Tuckernuck and five transects on Muskeget. A total of 42 people-days of fieldwork were spread across four field trips in June, July, August and September of 2013. Among 3,935 specimens collected on Tuckernuck, we found 38 species. The most common species were *Myrmica americana*, *Aphaenogaster rudis*, *Crematogaster lineolata*, *Lasius cf. niger*, and *Solenopsis cf. texana*. Five species, including *Lasius cf. niger*, *Camponotus pennsylvanicus*, *Camponotus neartica*, *Formica argentea*, and *Myrmica rubra*, were not reported in Ellison's synthesis of Nantucket's ants. Among 16,621 specimens collected on Muskeget, we identified seven species all of which were also found on Tuckernuck. Muskeget's ant fauna is dominated by *Crematogaster lineolata*, which comprised 98% of the specimens, followed by *Lasius cf. niger* with 1.7% of the specimens.

Our predictions of species diversity were underestimates for Tuckernuck (38 observed and 33 maximum predicted) and overestimates for Muskeget (11 minimum predicted and 7 observed). Using published equations of ant island biodiversity to predict diversity on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget yielded results that were not consistent among the islands. Together our findings suggest area alone is not a good predictor of ant diversity on Tuckernuck and Muskeget. The higher than predicted diversity of ants for Tuckernuck may be the result of high habitat diversity for its area and lower human disturbance rates when compared to Nantucket and Muskeget. The lower than predicted diversity of Muskeget may be the result of reduced number of habitats and its higher disturbance rates when compared to Nantucket and Tuckernuck.

An unexpected finding was the high densities of the invasive ant *Lasius cf. niger* on both islands. Only one individual of this species, captured in 2011 in southeastern Massachusetts, had been documented previously on the East Coast. Another invasive species, *Myrmica rubra*, was documented for the first time on Tuckernuck, but has not yet been seen on Nantucket.

Introduction

Ellison (2012) has recently described the ant fauna of Nantucket Island based on 384 samples collected from 2000 to 2009. He sorted over 32,000 individual ants, and identified 58 species. Remarkably, this diversity represents about 50% of the species and 70% of the genera found in all of New England.

Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands were united just 2500-3000 years ago (Gutierrez et al 2003) and now form an east-west archipelago in Nantucket Sound. The recent land connection suggests that Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands, like Nantucket, may be more species rich than expected because of relict populations (Crowell 1986). But Nantucket has a land area of about 125 km² whereas the published land areas of Tuckernuck and Muskeget are only about 3.6 km² and 1.2 km² respectively (3% and 1% of Nantucket's area respectively). Accordingly, biogeography theory (Munroe 1947 cited in Brown and Lomolina 1989, MacArthur and Wilson 1967, Losos and Ricklefs 2009) predicts reduced ant species richness for these smaller islands. Although significantly smaller, Tuckernuck has many of the same habitats (sandplain grasslands, sandplain heathlands, scrub oak shrublands, beaches and sand dunes, salt marshes, and fresh water marshes) found on Nantucket while Muskeget has far fewer habitats (sand dunes, salt marshes, fresh water marshes).

With this perspective in mind, we set out to predict and document the ant diversity of Tuckernuck and Muskeget islands, which have been sampled, but not sampled systematically (Ellison 2012 and personal communication). Two questions focused our research: 1) Do Tuckernuck and Muskeget have unusually high ant diversity as Ellison (2102) found on Nantucket? 2) Can the equilibrium theory of biogeography theory explain patterns of species richness of the islands?

Based on the equilibrium island biogeography theory,

$$S=cA^z \quad (1)$$

where

S is the number of species predicted,

c is an empirical constant,

A is the area of island (km²) and

z is a constant general thought to vary between 0.15 and 0.35,

we predicted the number of species on Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands (Table 1). We began by assuming the number of species on Nantucket $S= 58$ and that z could be 0.15, 0.25, 0.35 from which we calculated the corresponding c 's to be 28.11, 17.34, 10.70 (Table 1). Then the predicted species numbers ranged from 16 to 33 for Tuckernuck and 11 to 29 for Muskeget (Table 1).

Methods and study sites

Field sampling: We visited Tuckernuck Island on June 26th-28th, July 7th- 9th and August 8th - 10th of 2013 and sampled 10 different sites labeled airstrip, dune, forest, grass-lands, marsh, meadow, old growth forest, pine forest, slough, swamp (Figure 1). The GPS coordinates and a short description for each transect are give in Table 2. These transect names reflect the general description of what we saw when sampling for ants. The names are not based on formal analysis of habitats or from maps in which habitat are designated by ecologists or land managers. Based on consultation with Lesley Sneddon of NatureServe we believe the habitats we sampled encompass Northern Atlantic Coastal Tidal Plain Salt Marsh, Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain Dune and Swale, Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain Maritime Forest.

We visited Muskeget Island on August 8th-9th and September 22th -24th 2013 and sampled five different sites (Table 2) which we generalized as dunes, sand grasslands, sand plain with low shrubs (Figure 2). The habitats fall under the habitats titled Northern Atlantic Coastal Tidal Plain Salt Marsh and Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain Dune and Swale as described above.

On each island we used pitfall traps, baits, and hand-collecting methods (ALL protocol, Agosti and Alonso 2000, Ipser et al. 2004, Ellison et al 2007, Ellison 2012). The Ants of the Leaf Litter protocol (ALL protocol) prescribes taking litter samples, in which one collects a sample of leaf litter and then extracts the ants found in the sample. However, habitats in our study rarely had leaf litter, so we were only able to collect litter along a few forested transects. For Tuckernuck, in addition to the transect work, we collected a small number of ants during opportunistic sampling along roads (second to last column Table 3).

The details of field sampling are as follows. At each site twenty pitfall traps (500 ml plastic jars with screw tops) were set ten meters apart in a relatively straight line. (One exception was the pine forest transect in which we looped back through the trees to stay within the habitat.) Each pitfall trap was filled with 20 ml of propylene glycol for preservation of the specimens. In order to prevent propylene glycol from evaporating and to keep dew and rain water out we used cardboard roofs fixed above the pitfall trap using metal stakes and rubber bands (Figure 3). The traps were set for 24 to 48 hours. Next to each pitfall trap we also laid out baits. Either one-half of a crumbed short bread cookie or a spoonful of canned tuna packed in oil was placed about half a meter away from the pitfall trap and flagged to make them easier to find. The baits were checked the same day at least three to six hours after they had been laid out. Ants were collected at bait sites by hand or with a pooter (aspirator) and stored in plastic centrifuge tubes secured with plastic tops containing o-ring seals. In the middle of each transect we hand-sampled a 10m x 10m plot for 1 to 2 man-hours (Ellison et al. 2012). Ants were preserved in centrifuge tubes in 90% ethanol.

Lab work: Samples were cleaned in the lab and sorted using dissecting microscopes and specimens stored in vials with 90% ethanol. Representative ant species are currently being pinned and will be deposited at the Harvard Museum of Comparative Zoology in Cambridge and the Maria Mitchell Museum in Nantucket.

Species identification: Ants were identified using A Field Guide to the Ants of New England (Ellison et al. 2012). Stefan Cover, the curator of the ant collection at the Harvard University Museum of Comparative Zoology, checked and corrected our identifications.

Analysis: The number of ants of each species was counted in each pitfall trap, bait trap, hand sample and litter sample and from the opportunistic samples. Data were entered into a Google Doc spreadsheet and summarized using pivot-tables. (The data table is available upon request. After our manuscript for publication is completed, we plan to deposit the raw data table in a data repository such as the California Digital Library or Dryad.)

Results

On Tuckernuck Island we found a 38 species (Table 3) in a total of 3,935 samples. The five most common species were *Myrmica americana*, *Aphaenogaster rudis*, *Crematogaster lineolata*, *Lasius cf. niger*, and *Solenopsis cf. texana*. Three of these species, *Myrmica americana*, *Lasius cf. niger*, and *Solenopsis cf. texana* were found predominantly on one transect, the grasslands, dunes, airstrip, respectively (Table 3) where as *Aphaenogaster rudis* was found on 8 of 10 transects and *Crematogaster lineolata* was found on every transect (Table 3). Three (*Lasius cf. niger*, *Tetramorium caespitum*, and *Myrmica rubra*) of the 38 species are non-native, invasive species in New England. We found 362 *Lasius cf. niger* individuals spanning seven of the ten transects sampled (Table 3). Three species, *Camponotus neartica*, *Formica integra*, *Temnothorax curvispinosis*, were found only among the sample of opportunistically collected ants.

On Muskeget Island we found a total of 7 species (Table 4). By far the most common species was *Crematogaster lineolata*, a native ant, comprising over 98% of the 16,613 specimens and found in all five transects. The next most common ant was *Lasius cf. niger* with 294 specimens totaling 1.7% of the specimens collected. We found very small numbers of the five other species (Table 4). *Crematogaster lineolata* dominated all transects except the dune habitat where *Lasius cf. niger* was the most common species.

The predictions of species diversity based on island biogeography theory (Table 1) were not high enough for Tuckernuck (38 observed vs. 33 maximum predicted) and too high for Muskeget (11 minimum predicted vs. 7 observed).

Discussion

Tuckernuck: We documented 38 species of ants on Tuckernuck Island. This is a higher number than expected (Table 1, but see Table 6 and discussion below). Thirty-four of these species are also found on Nantucket. The four species not found on Nantucket include *Lasius cf. niger*, *Camponotus pennsylvanicus*, *Camponotus neartica*, and *Myrmica rubra*. Perhaps most surprising is that *Camponotus pennsylvanicus* was not found on Nantucket because it is a very common ant in New England. The existence and large numbers of *Lasius cf. niger* was not anticipated. *Lasius cf. niger* is a species heretofore found in only one sample by Pat Kearns of UMass Boston in 2011 in the Great Sippewisset salt marsh near Falmouth, Massachusetts. We predict this species will be found on Nantucket if searched for on sand dunes and other open

sandy habitats. It is also of note that we found one example of *Myrmica rubra*, a species that is invading New England (Grodén et al. 2005, Wetterer and Radchenko 2011, Eldridge Adams, personal communication). Recently DeFisher and Bonter (2013) noted the negative impacts of *Myrmica rubra* on Herring gull reproduction in New Hampshire.

Muskeget: We documented 7 species of ants on Muskeget Island. This is a lower number than expected (Table 1, but see Table 6 and discussion below). *Crematogaster lineolata* made up 98% of the ants caught on Muskeget (Table 4). The ant species resident on Muskeget are found in similar habitats on Nantucket and Tuckernuck (Table 5). The number of ants gathered on Muskeget is four times the number of specimens collected on Tuckernuck with only half of the collecting effort. High density of populations on islands are known (MacArthur et al 1972) and correlated with the low species richness.

Lasius cf. niger was the second most common ant on Muskeget (Table 4). As noted above *Lasius cf. niger* has been found only once before in New England. We checked samples collected by McKenna-Foster from 2005 for *Lasius cf. niger* (Table 4) and what was previously identified as *Lasius neoniger* is now recognized by Ellison and Cover (personal communications) to be *Lasius cf. niger*. This means that *Lasius cf. niger* has been resident in southern New England at least 9 years.

Ellison processed collections made by Andrew McKenna-Foster from Muskeget Island in 2005 and also found seven species including *Crematogaster lineolata*, *Ponera pennsylvanica*, *Formica argentea*, *Lasius cf. niger*, *Tapinoma sessile*, *Lasius alienus*, and *Aphaenogaster rudis*. Four of the seven species were found by both surveys, *Crematogaster lineolata*, *Ponera pennsylvanica*, *Formica argentea*, and *Lasius cf. niger* (Table 5). This suggests that there is a significant turnover rate of species or that the relatively rare species are hard to collect in a fauna dominated by *Crematogaster lineolata*. We suspect the lack of habitat diversity on Muskeget, blowing sands and island wash-overs from high seas and strong wind associated with hurricanes and Nor'easters could be responsible for the relatively low ant diversity observed.

Patterns of ant diversity on Nantucket, Tuckernuck, and Muskeget: To further explore the application of equilibrium island biogeography to the patterns of ant diversity on the three islands, we used parameters for equation (1) found in the literature to make additional predictions (Table 6). (Note that one should be cautious when comparing predictions because the range of island sizes, biomes, mainland diversity of ants, habitat diversity of the islands and distance differ in the literature studies compared to the islands of the Nantucket group.) All calculations for Nantucket (29 to 50 species) are below its 58 recorded species and thus support Ellison's (2012) conclusion that Nantucket is rich in species. The parameters from Broomsmma et al 1987, based on observations of ants on the Frisian Islands off the coast of the Netherlands, predict only 2 species for an island the size of Muskeget. These calculations and their data show that a low lying island of similar size could have diversity as low or lower than Muskeget. Using the parameters from Clark et al 2011, based on observations of ants on the Boston Harbor islands, we calculated 38 species for an island the size of Tuckernuck, as we indeed found. The harbor islands of Boston are much closer to the mainland than is Tuckernuck and have a different geology. We see that individual equations predict some of our findings but one equation alone did not accurately predict diversity on both islands. We conclude that equilibrium island

biodiversity theory based on area alone is not sufficient to explain the diversity of ants on Nantucket's archipelago. Additional frameworks, such as the multi-scale area model (Lomolino and Weiser 2001) and area-habitat model (Triantis et al 2003), need to be considered.

In summary we think that the Nantucket and Muskeget have relatively high ant diversity while Muskeget is low. Nantucket and Tuckernuck are relatively high because of relatively high habitat diversity and their short-term temporal isolation from the mainland leading to supersaturated with ant species from with relic populations. On the other hand, Muskeget, given its land area and close proximate and similar history to Tuckernuck and Nantucket, has low ant diversity. We suggest the low lying topography of Muskeget, exposing it to blowing sands and island wash-overs from high seas and strong wind associated with hurricanes and Nor'easters, results in relatively low habitat diversity and relatively high disturbance rates, both of which contribute to its low ant diversity. These ideas for the divergent ant diversity patterns on Tuckernuck and Muskeget need to be subject to further scrutiny with additional data before scientists will believe their validity.

Acknowledgments

The Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative, the Department of Biology at UMass Boston, National Science Foundation REU grant to UMass Boston, National Science Foundation EF 0849982 grant to Hong Cui at the University of Arizona, and the UMass Boston Field Station provided financial support or defrayed expenses.

Melissa Scubelek was a generous hostess during our visits to Tuckernuck Land Trust Field Station. Crocker Snow graciously gave us access to his cabin during our stay on Muskeget Island in September.

Many landowners on Tuckernuck gave us access to their property.

Julie Merrill, Melissa Scubelek, and Owen LaFarge helped with fieldwork.

Aaron Ellison and Stefan Cover provided invaluable guidance about the collecting and identifying ants and about the biogeography of the ants of New England. Dick Viet and Sarah Oktay shared their extensive knowledge of the natural history and biology of the islands. We also thank Gary Alpert, Sarah Oktay, Andrew McKenna-Foster, Karen Beattie, Crocker Snow Jr., Bam LaFarge, Jennifer Karberg, Melissa Scubelek, Emily MacKinnon for the words of advice at various stages of the research.

Blair Perkins, Phil Marks, Peter and Mark Souza, and Bam LaFarge provide transportation. Sarah Oktay, Emily MacKinnon, Peter Boyce and Al Coffin gave us helpful advice about how best to get to from island to island.

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Figure 1. Google map of the Tuckernuck transects. The corresponding GPS coordinates are given in Table 2.

Figure 2. Google map of the Muskeget transects. The corresponding GPS coordinates are given in Table 2.

Figure 3. Standard 500ml pitfall trap fixed with a cardboard roof using metal stakes as described in methods

Table 1. Prediction of the number of species of ants on Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands based on the simple island area model assuming there are 58 species of ants on Nantucket.

		Assumed Z values		
		0.15	0.25	0.35
		c values for Nantucket S = 58		
		28.11	17.35	10.70
	Area (km ²)	Predicted Species Number		
Tuckernuck Island	3.2	33	23	16
Muskeget Island	1.2	29	18	11

Table 2. GPS coordinates for the start and end of all transects on both Tuckernuck and Muskeget islands with a general observational description

Island	Habitat	Transect Name	Start Coordinates		End Coordinates		Description
			Location N	Location W (-)	Location N	Location W (-)	
Tuckernuck	Marsh	A	41.306067	-70.265017	41.307400	-70.263750	Salt water marsh, moist mud 3" thick.
Tuckernuck	Forest	B	41.302033	-70.254967	41.302100	-70.257233	Thick with low level shrubs and trees, shady with thick leaf litter
Tuckernuck	Grasslands	C	41.297200	-70.257550	41.297350	-70.259733	Open area, very sunny, plants not taller than 8"
Tuckernuck	Sand Dune	D	41.309033	-70.276317	41.310333	-70.277733	Open exposed dry sand with intermittent patches of dune grass
Tuckernuck	Meadow	E(AA)	41.304467	-70.250367	41.304900	-70.248630	dry soil with tall grass in open field
Tuckernuck	Slough	F(BB)	41.300400	-70.249233	41.299200	-70.250067	Lowest point of island, wetland, thick mud.
Tuckernuck	Swamp	G(CC)	41.307317	-70.255167	41.307067	-70.254667	Very wet thick mud amidst dense trees.
Tuckernuck	Airstrip	H(DD)	41.299217	-70.247750	41.297517	-70.247967	Very disturbed mowed grass. Dry and exposed
Tuckernuck	Old Oak Forest	I(EE)	41.304050	-70.255950	41.304683	-70.256517	Forest filled with old low height oak trees, shady moist, with thick leaf litter and humus.
Tuckernuck	Pine Forest	J(FF)	41.306183	-70.254283	41.306250	-70.254483	Tallest trees on island rare patch of pine trees with leaf litter consisting of pine needles, shady moist.
Muskeget	Grassy Sand (A)	V	41.335600	-70.295933	41.336067	-70.293783	Sand with patches of low shrubs and grass
Muskeget	Grassy Sand (B)	W	41.336100	-70.293800	41.336650	-70.295967	Sand with patches of low shrubs and grass
Muskeget	Sand Dune	X	41.334150	-70.308117	41.333267	-70.306517	Sand with patches of dune grass, exposed, and dry
Muskeget	Grass and Trees	Y	41.334400	-70.300850	41.335950	-70.300583	Grasslands with the tallest/oldest trees found on the island
Muskeget	Grass, Pine, Moss	Z	41.336617	-70.302283	41.335083	-70.302583	Grasslands with patches of pine trees and moss covered soil

Table 3. Summary of ants species found on Tuckernuck Island by transect. Systematic sampling at 10 transects augmented by opportunistic hand sampling yielded 3,935 ant specimens and 38 species.

Species	Transects										Total	
	Airstrip	Dune	Forest	Grass-lands	Marsh	Meadow	Old Growth Forest	Pine forest	Slough	Swamp		Opportunistic Samples
<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>	60		29		2	38	148	61	140	8		486
<i>Aphaenogaster treatae</i>	56			33		7		9				105
<i>Camponotus nearctica</i>											1	1
<i>Camponotus pennsylvanicus</i>			1				8				1	10
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>	111	3	73	44	19	98	1	37	53	3	1	443
<i>Dolichoderus plagiatus</i>							2					2
<i>Formica argentea</i>		1	1					2				4
<i>Formica dolosa</i>				7		1						8
<i>Formica exsectoides</i>							15					15
<i>Formica incerta</i>	4				2				1			7
<i>Formica integra</i>											1	1
<i>Formica neogagates</i>							1	1	1			3
<i>Formica obscuriventris</i>							16				1	17
<i>Formica pallidefulva</i>	3											3
<i>Formica subsericae</i>	7	1	13				20	1			1	43
<i>Lasius alienus</i>	1	14	1		7		9	6	22	13	2	75
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>	3	255			5	24	2	6	31			326
<i>Lasius claviger</i>							18	1			1	20
<i>Lasius flavus</i>				3	1							4
<i>Lasius neoniger</i>								1			1	2
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>	44			3		3					1	51
<i>Myrmica af. scu</i>			1	1					5			7
<i>Myrmica af. smi</i>								10	1			11
<i>Myrmica americana</i>	21		1	1839							1	1862

<i>Myrmica fracticornis</i>	1		1				1					3
<i>Myrmica incompleta</i>			2	1			1					4
<i>Myrmica pineоторum</i>				2					3			5
<i>Myrmica punctiventris</i>			2				19	12			1	34
<i>Myrmica rubra</i>										1		1
<i>Myrmica sculptulis</i>					2							2
<i>Nylanderia parvula</i>	1			1		1		16		2		21
<i>Ponera pennsylvanica</i>						2	2			1	1	6
<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>	229					3	5	13	41			291
<i>Solenopsis molesta</i>	7								26		1	34
<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>			5				5	1	2		1	14
<i>Temnothorax ambiguus</i>									1			1
<i>Temnothorax curvispinosis</i>											1	1
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>			1		1					9	1	12
Grand Total	548	274	133	1932	39	177	276	177	326	36	17	3935

Table 4. Summary of ant samples on Muskeget Island. Seven species were found spanning a total of 5 transects totaling 16,621 specimens.

Species	Transect					Grand Total
	Grass & Trees	Grass, Pine, & moss	Grassy sand (A)	Grassy sand (B)	Sand dune	
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>	1100	1586	7175	6404	22	16287
<i>Formica argentea</i>					24	24
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>	3	1	70	78	142	294
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>				1		1
<i>Ponera pennsylvanica</i>					1	1
<i>Solenopsis cf. texana</i>	3					3
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>					3	3
Grand Total	1108	1591	7245	6485	192	16621

Table 5. All the species caught on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Islands from salt marsh, beach dune, and sandplain grassland habitats. There are many more habitats found on Nantucket and Tuckernuck but these are the only habitats found on Muskeget.

Species	Nantucket Is. Ellison (2012)			Tuckernuck Island 2013 (this study)			Muskeget Island	
	Salt marsh	Beach dune	Sandplain grassland	Salt marsh	Beach dune	Sandplain grassland	Ellison & McKenna-Foster unpub. 2006	this study 2013
<i>Ponera pennsylvanica</i>		X	X				X	X
<i>Dolichoderus plagiatus</i>	X							
<i>Tapinoma sessile</i>		X	X				X	
<i>Formica argentea</i>					X		X	X
<i>Formica subserica</i>	X	X	X		X			
<i>Lasius alienus</i>				X	X		X	
<i>Lasius flavus</i>		X		X	X	X		
<i>Lasius neoniger</i>	X	X	X					
<i>Lasius cf. niger</i>				X	X	X	X	X
<i>Lasius subglaber</i>		X						
<i>Nylanderia parvula</i>		X						
<i>Aphaenogaster rudis</i>		X	X	X			X	
<i>Crematogaster lineolata</i>		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Monomorium emarginatum</i>			X			X		X
<i>Solenopsis molesta</i>			X	X				X
<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	X	X	X	X				X

Table 6. Predictions of ant diversity on Nantucket, Tuckernuck and Muskeget Island using equations derived in other ant island biodiversity studies.

Author	Location	z	Island		
			Nantucket	Tuckernuck	Muskeget
Broomsma et al 1987	Frisian islands off the coast of the Netherlands	0.5406	29	4	2
Rizali et al 2010	Thousand Islands off the coast of Indonesia	0.1059	37	25	22
Clark et al 2011	Boston Harbor islands	0.0819	50	38	34